

LANGUAGE AS A SYNERGETIC SYSTEM

*Sh. Nosirova*¹

Abstract:

This article discusses the uniqueness of language as a synergistic system, synergistic methods of forming students' worldview, and the synergistic importance of language in ensuring the sustainable development of society.

Key words: synergetics, student-youth, self-organization, synergetic outlook, society, spirituality, education.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/rdgz1r47>

The idea of language as a linguistic system originated in the linguistic theories of Ferdinand de Saussure, J.R. Firth, Benjamin Lee Whorf, Louis Hjelmslev, and Michael Halliday. Paradigmatic principle - the process of using language involves choosing from a set of certain options. "System" is used in two ways in systemic functional linguistics. Systematic functional linguistics uses the idea of a system to refer to a language as a whole (eg "language system"). In this context, Jay Lemke describes language as an open, dynamic system. There is also the concept of "system" used by J.R. Firth, where linguistic systems provide the basis for structural elements. Halliday argues that, unlike system, it is a concept in the sense used by Firth that exists only in Firth's linguistic theory. Today, synergy is considered as one of the main aspects of forming a new outlook of students. Interest of students to work based on new trends is on the agenda as one of the urgent tasks. Creative and prognostic thinking helps students to work as a self-organizing system. Properly developing a new unique style will greatly contribute to the learning process. Synergetics includes the field of interpersonal communication that helps the continuous development of the higher education system. Synergetic cognition is focused on the process of communicative activity. Synergetics is conceptually an open system. It forms interdisciplinary teacher and student-young people communication. Synergetic thinking activates the development of the pedagogical process and its results. The analysis of this problem in the scientific literature shows that the synergetic approach considers the educational system as a complex system and formulates certain principles for the development of this system. These terms are: Openness, Complexity, Nonlinearity, Instability.

Today, synergy is considered as one of the main aspects of forming a new outlook of students. Interest of students to work based on new trends is on the agenda as one of the urgent tasks. Creative and prognostic thinking helps students to work as a self-organizing system. Properly developing a new unique style will greatly contribute to the learning process. Synergistic mechanisms, such as openness, non-linearity, considerations are the leaders in creating modern terms of education and upbringing of students and defining them as a unique system. Language Synergy can be of great help in creating modern terms for teaching and educating students. Language is a scientific field of systematically

¹ *Nosirova Shoira Olimovna, Samarqand davlat chet tillar instituti o'qituvchisi*

organized systems, which is developing as a synergistic system, and the system of professional training of young specialists can also be included in it. This approach creates new opportunities for students' self-organization within the framework of multidimensionality, complexity and alternation of cognitive processes. It is important to recognize the important role of randomness in students' self-development. It should be noted that language systems, which include several complex system components forming an integrated synergistic system, are actually implemented in conditions of diversity, randomness, spontaneity and unpredictability. The problem is that the future young specialist should have the ability and professional mobility to quickly react to the changes that constantly appear in practical and scientific activity. In short, the synergetic system of the language is one of the main issues of improving the training of students in modern higher education institutions. Through the approach of the language as a synergetic system, various aspects of human life are studied.

In today's rapidly developing world, there is a great demand for the formation of a multi-purpose, global vision, capable of analyzing the complex problems of society, ready to solve various problems. The changes taking place in today's world show that there is a need for a completely new approach to the current education system, which implies a strategy for its further development. In the approach of language as a synergistic system, the humanization of education is an important part of growth in all fields. It helps solve global environmental and spiritual problems using synergistic methods. This is practically the only way for the development of society and nature to overcome the threat of ecological crisis. In such conditions, modern society determines the development of the individual, the correct choice of his cultural consciousness, which is a necessary condition for the continuous development of civilization. The approach of the language as a synergistic system in the higher education system is currently considered as one of the main aspects of the formation of new thinking in students. In the educational process, in the analysis of the student's personality, advanced thinking of students helps to consider the student as a unique system. This system includes professional knowledge, it is important to achieve more success in education, to recognize new trends in the world. Within the framework of social values, issues of modernization of education are filled with new creative content. In such conditions, the level of professional training of students is of course important. It is very important to know the subject well and master the teaching methods. A self-developing system capable of developing new modern approaches to individual education of students should be formed.

It is a positive news that students and young people can independently choose the subjects to be taught at the educational institution, and even the teachers themselves determine them. Professors-teachers should keep in mind that a new methodology is a great necessity, accepting the linguistic synergistic paradigm. In modern Russian scientific pedagogical studies (M.V. Boguslavsky, A.N. Dakhin, M.P. Karpenko, I.A. Kolesnikova, V.N. Pomogaybin, etc.), the problem of transition to a new secondary school with its new methodology is becoming more and more important. It will be a reasonable response to the requirements of modern developed society, its main problems and technologies. Currently, there is a great demand for creating conditions for students to be trained on their personal educational trajectory and at the level of complexity corresponding to it. A student is now a self-esteeming individual with his own developing life logic and tendencies. He is at the center of the modern pedagogical process and can be seen as a single integrated person. Of course, the idea of an individual approach to education is not new. It has been widely used even in ancient times and throughout the history of education. For example, they put forward the alternative of "collective education", which was widespread in the Middle Ages.

In Russia, individual education has become a traditional form. This is deeply rooted in the mentality of the Russian people. Learning itself changes. From the very beginning of a student's choice of academic trajectory, a table of unknowns arises for these students. Then, students are determined to learn conscientiously, taking into account a realistic assessment of their professional level. The new synergetic paradigm of teaching is considered very useful because it implies self-organization and self-development. Therefore, this approach can be called the theory of self-developing systems. Here, the student is also a system. The approach of language as a synergetic system is considered as one of the main aspects of forming a new worldview of students. A synergistic system of language tries to overcome the linear thinking that now dominates. According to some well-known Russian and foreign scientists, such thinking is definitely not enough. It can distort complex non-linear reality. This can be interpreted as a human dimension. The synergetic system of language is of great importance for higher education, because it is connected with the emergence of a new paradigm. Synergetics covers the field of interpersonal communication that contributes to the continuous development of the higher education system. Synergetic cognition is focused on the process of communicative activity. Synergetics is conceptually an open system. It forms interdisciplinary teacher-student communication. Synergetic thinking activates the development of the pedagogical process and its results. The analysis of this problem in the scientific literature shows that the synergetic approach considers the educational system as a complex system and formulates certain principles for the development of this system. These terms are: Openness, Complexity, Nonlinearity, Instability. Applying synergistic ideas to the educational process is effective. One of the important requirements of the modernization of the educational process is the integration of the scientific education space and the self-organization of the students, assimilating the cultural values. A synergistic analysis of the ecological problem means that the ecocentric approach to nature and the desire of people to save the planet oppose the destruction of nature. This new ecological thinking will contribute to the survival of all mankind. Synergistic ideas are more successful when combined with natural sciences and humanities. Synergistic ideas in education are considered as a deep scientific problem. It is of great importance to solve the main theoretical tasks of self-organization by designing, diagnosing and forecasting the development of the language teaching process.

The use of the synergistic system of the language in monitoring the educational process can solve many problems. It should be borne in mind that didactic aspects should be developed in order to adapt synergistic ideas to educational content. Such approaches can be called the general theory of self-developing systems. It can become the basis of the entire world scientific landscape. Attention is paid to the synergetic approach in the educational process as a development model. Attractors are said to help open closed systems. The educational system, like other complex organized systems, has a number of unique features. These are: originality, originality, subjectivity, variety. Effective communication with students is of great importance. Teachers should create unique individual programs, learning trajectories and methods, new methods based on a synergistic approach to language. Of all the necessary qualities, the most important are systematic thinking and knowledge, and the ability to work in a team. In the current conditions, the system of formation of research skills should include:

- a general view of the formulation of the problem;
- development of synergetic reflex;
- systematization of language knowledge;
- discuss possible topics;

- teaching practical skills;
- practical work in learning the scientific method.

Modern scientists use many different approaches in their work. For this, they choose different methodological bases. All these approaches can be combined synergistically because it is interdisciplinary and cross-cultural in nature. In conclusion, it can be said that we present several main synergistic mechanisms in the formation of a new worldview of students and young people: self-education, acquisition of self-education methods, adaptation to newly modified structures of knowledge and behavior. "tooth, dialogic thinking and reconstruction of lifestyle, non-linear and changes of thinking, uniqueness of language. Therefore, we can conclude that a unique style and a new approach to education is very necessary at the moment. The uniqueness of the language as a synergetic system is one of the issues that cannot be delayed in creating modern terms for teaching and educating students.

References:

- [1]. T. Dombrovan, *An Introduction to Linguistic Synergetics* (Cambridge Scholars Publishing, Cambridge, 2018).
- [2]. E.N. Knyazeva, S.P. Kurdyumov, *Foundations of synergetics: aggravation, self-organization, tempomir* (SPb, Aleteya, 2002).
- [3]. H. Haken, *Secrets of Nature. Synergetics (Doctrine of Interaction, Yzhevsk, 2003).*
- [4]. H. Haken, *Synergetics: Is self-organization governed by universal principles? The Evolutionary Vision: Toward A Unifying Paradigm of Physical, Biological and Sociocultural Evolution, 15–24* (2019).
- [5]. E.N. Knyazeva, S.P. Kurdyumov, *Synergetics: Time Non-Linearity and Coevolution (Landscape, Moscow, 2007).*
- [6]. Turayev B.O. *Man, his belief, society, universe: problems of development and present time. -T., 2015*
- [7]. Turayev B.O. *Universe // Philosophy: a brief annotated dictionary. - T.: Sharq, 2004.*
- [8]. Turayev B.O. *Selected works. 2nd floor. T.: 2015.*
- [9]. Turayev B.O. *Modern concepts of natural science. T.: Tafakkur, 2009.*
- [10]. Turayev B.O. *Existence: essence, forms, characteristics. -T: Institute of Philosophy and Law, 2011.*
- [11]. Turayev B.O. *Synergetic space and time landscape of the universe // Synergetic paradigm: problems and opportunities. Materials of the scientific-theoretical seminar. -T.: 2013;*
- [12]. Melikuzievich, K. P., & Abdurashidovich, T. M. (2021). *International peace as a universal value. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 1(02), 73-78. M.,*
- [13]. Axtamova F. U., Yarqulova D. M. *Exploring the Key Features of Four Learning Styles: A Guide to Personalized Education //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 21. – C. 27-30.*